

ISic0908

I.Sicily inscription 0908

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

stone

Object

wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Δατείβου

2. τόπος

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 492538

EDCS 39102065

PHI 140389

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae*

Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0091 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0908. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340021>